

1 **Ku70 and Ku80 (XRCC6 and XRCC5) levels influence Xist activation.**

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6 We demonstrate here by study of transcription in cells with that Ku70/Ku80, genes that participate in DNA
7 repair-associated processes, including genetic rearrangement events that occur during VDJ recombination
8 of immunoglobulin gene segments, in non-homologous end joining (NHEJ), as well as in maintenance of
9 the telomeres (Rif1), are regulators of Xist activation, expression not associated with its function during
10 female development in the embryo. XRCC6 loss was accompanied by activation of RECQL and Rad54L2,
11 and repression of CHEK1, ATM and MRE11A, while XRCC5 depletion was accompanied by activation of
12 Rad9A and Rad50. Xist RNA and Xist interacting proteins were controlled by Ku70/Ku80. A Xist
13 localization component, SPEN, was activated concomitant with Xist activation resulting from genetic
14 depletion of XRCC6, as was a recently identified component of the Xist RNP complex and target of Xist
15 autosomal gene regulation, ILF2. Further support for a functionally relevant relationship between
16 Ku70/Ku80 and Xist gene regulation was repression of the LSD2-associated nuclear factor PHF21A
17 (BHC80), an Xist interacting protein we recently described as a component of a novel Xist RNP complex.
18 The data provide further evidence indicating a specific role for Xist as a participant and/or regulator of
19 DNA repair processes. Therefore, expression of the Xist non-coding RNA (and thus Xist function) is
20 associated with a multitude of cell type-specific and broadly used cellular functions that utilize DNA repair
21 machinery.
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